

Leaching characteristics of selected Indian coal combustion residues and its environmental implications

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Abstract : In India, the present management practice of handling coal combustion residue (CCR) involves a combination of two strategies. The first one involves maximum possible utilization in all the avenues followed by the disposal of unutilized CCR as waste in landfill sites. In this study, CCR samples were collected from four different thermal power plants and analyzed for their leaching behavior by short and long term leaching studies. The leachates were found to exist in neutral to slightly alkaline range during the major course of study. Amongst the total twenty-three elements studied for leaching only nine like sodium, potassium, calcium, magnesium, manganese, copper, iron, zinc and lead were observed in leachates. For all the nine leached elements high concentrations were observed initially which reduced considerably with time. Chromium, nickel, cobalt, cadmium, selenium, aluminum, silver, arsenic, boron, barium, vanadium, antimony, molybdenum and mercury were observed to be present below the detection limit (0.01 ppm) during the entire study period of 1100 days. The results obtained further suggest that leaching from CCRs as such do not pose any significant environmental impacts to the water disposal system.

Keywords : Coal combustion residues, leachates, fly ash, bottom ash, pond ash.

Introduction

The coal/lignite based thermal power plants account for more than 66% of the installed capacity of electricity generation in India¹. Coal inherently contains various kinds of elements which are thermally transformed during the processes of ash formation owing to high temperatures. These elements remain associated with ash particles in various ways²⁻⁹. There has been a growing concern for trace element contamination of surface and ground water due to leaching from the huge ash ponds situated in and around the water resources of the country. In India, wet disposal method is generally followed. In this process fly ash is mixed with water in 1 : 20 ratio and the formed slurry is pumped through pipelines into the disposal pond. Wet fly ash handling methods can degrade the pozzolanic

characteristics of the material¹⁰⁻¹². Terrestrial disposal of CCRs has been regarded as a potential source of contamination due to enrichment and surface association of trace elements in the ash particles¹³⁻²⁰.

Accumulation of these residues in ponds for long makes the ground water vulnerable to contamination due to leachate percolation¹². The polluted leachate generated by rainwater percolating through fly ash dumps traverses into the underlying soil to reach ground water causing deterioration in its quality. The ground water environment is more vulnerable than surface water, due to low velocity under low permeability and possible accumulation of leached elements in the ground water. The quality of leachate formed depends upon the quantity of external solvent entering the landfills and the type of material in the landfill²¹.

The extraction of water soluble major-elements and trace-elements from fly ash in open and closed leaching systems have been studied earlier²²⁻³⁰. Much concern has been paid to the leaching behavior and the possible contamination, especially for the aquatic environment, when ash is in contact with water.

The aim of this study is to investigate the leaching behavior of CCRs currently disposed in Korba and to assess the potential influence on ground water quality. The methods adopted in the study include short term leaching studies under rigorous conditions and long term leaching studies which simulate field conditions. These results provide the basis for the design of ash treating systems which are helpful to evolve an environmentally benign ash management system.

Materials and methods :

Sampling :

Korba town is the major source of electricity in the Chhattisgarh State. It is located at 22.35° North latitude and 82.68° East longitude. The CCR samples were collected from four different thermal power plants in Korba, Korba Super Thermal Power Station (KSTPS), Chhattisgarh State Electricity Board-East (CSEB-E), Chhattisgarh State Electricity Board-West (CSEB-W) and Balco Captive Power Plant (BCPP).

The fly ash samples were collected directly from the chimney bag house of the power plants. The heavier particles fall down under gravity and constitute the bottom ash. To dispose off the ash, wet disposal method is followed. The pond ash samples were collected at varying depths of ash ponds and mixed in appropriate portions. All the samples were mixed thoroughly to result representative samples.

Analytical techniques :

Leaching characteristics of the CCRs were studied using four different methods outlined below¹² :

(i) Strong Acid Digestion (for bulk composition analysis), (ii) 24 h shake test (ASTM D 398), (iii) Toxicity Characteristic Leachate Procedure (EPA 1311), (iv) ASTM Column Experiments (ASTM D 4874) and (v) Open Column Percolation Experiments.

Elemental analysis was carried out using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS-GBC-Avanta) and Systronics Flame Photometer model 128.

Acid digest test :

0.5 g of the oven-dried sample was moistened by 2 ml of perchloric acid. 10 ml of conc. HNO₃ was added to it and heated to dryness. Thereafter it was digested for 3-4 h after adding 20 ml of 10% HNO₃. It was filtered, made up to 100 ml and kept for analysis. Acid digest data provided the available concentration levels of trace elements in samples.

24 h shake test :

This is also a short term leaching study. This test is run for twenty-four hours and distilled water is used as a leaching medium. Two litres of distilled water was added to 80 g of CCR sample and closed tightly in an extraction bottle. This was followed by an end-on-end rotation at 30 rpm for 24 h. Later on, the extraction was performed in triplicate on each CCR sample and the three triplicates were then mixed to get the composite leachate sample. The leachate was filtered through Whatman no. 42 filter paper and stored for further analysis.

Toxicity characteristic leachate procedure :

The toxicity characteristic leachate procedure (TCLP) test was performed using the extraction fluid made of a buffered acidic medium (by adding 2 ml of conc. HNO₃) to run the test. The selection of the extraction fluid was made prior to running the test. To 5 g of sample, twenty times extraction fluid was added in the zero head extractor under pressure. The system was tightly closed and placed in an end over end rotary agitator for 18 h at 30 ± 2 rpm at a room temperature of about 25 °C. Leachate was pressure filtered using 0.7 μ pore size filter paper and stored in polypropylene bottles for further analysis.

ASTM column experiment :

5 g of sample was taken and then extraction fluid equal to twenty times the amount of sample was added in a zero head extractor under pressure. The system placed in an end-over-end rotary agitator for 18 h, at 30 ± 2 rpm at a room temperature. The extract was filtered using 0.7 micron pore size filter paper and kept for analysis. Leaching in this column was conducted under nitrogen atmosphere. The rate of percolation of the leaching medium was controlled by applying variable nitrogen pressure. The column set up involved packing the ash content as determined by ASTM standards.

Open column percolation experiments :

The columns were 10 cm in diameter and 60 cm in length. The column set up involved packing the ash content as determined by Proctor Test as given in Annual Book of ASTM Standards 11¹⁰, 1990. The top 7.5 cm of the column was left unpacked to allow for the addition and maintenance of the leaching medium. The column was packed with the specific type of CCR according to the natural permeability of the material. About 250 ml of distilled water (leaching medium) was added to the top of column once every alternate day and the leachate was collected from the Teflon tube opening at the bottom.

The CCR samples at optimum moisture content were placed in the column in layers, each layer being scratched with spatula before the second layer was placed to ensure proper interlocking of the material. The top of the column and polypropylene beakers were covered with common zip-lock plastic bags to prevent dust and other contamination. The open column percolation experiment tries to simulate the field condition and is the only experiment that predicts long term leaching behavior akin to the field conditions. For the purpose of comparison pond ash effluents were also monitored and compared with the laboratory study.

Leaching characteristics of CCRs :

The leaching of major elements has been extensively studied from CCR samples (Tables 1–5). The CCR samples normally contain a higher proportion of water-soluble constituents². Leachate analysis showed that the principal

cations in water extracts are calcium and sodium hence the anions may be dominated by CO_3^{2-} and OH^- ions. This is suggested by the open percolation column studies of CCR samples of various thermal power plants. Amongst all elements, highest concentration of Ca (1–79 ppm, Table 4) and Mg (1–98 ppm, Table 4) were found in the leachates. The leaching of elements like Cu, Fe, Zn, Pb, Cr, Ni, Co, Cd, Se, Al, Ag, As, B, Ba, V, Sb, Mo and Hg varied with the pH range (5.54–10.67, Table 5) of the leachates. It was further observed that initial leachates with high concentration of elements had acidic pH while the elemental concentrations decreased as the pH became alkaline in due course of time. This may be due to high dissolution of trace elements in acidic conditions. The leachates may have markedly different compositions, depending on the surface of CCRs, flue gas processing conditions, design of combustion systems *etc.*³¹.

Acid Digestion Test data provided the total available elemental content which can be leached out from the samples. Hence, its concentration was at elevated levels compared to the other tests (Table 5). TCLP leachate data gave comparatively lower elemental concentration of leachates which may be attributed to leaching in slightly acidic-buffered conditions. So, it does not represent the actual leaching behavior. Both these shake tests present the accelerated leaching because of rigorous leaching conditions. Thus these short-term leaching tests provide an immediate and rapid indication of leachable concentration levels of trace elements from CCRs (Table 5).

Table 1. Summary of the leachate analysis of KSTPS CCR samples

Parameters	FA	BA	PA	(IS : 2490, 1981)	
				Inland surface water	Onland for irrigation
pH	6.04–10.05	5.6–9.5	6.03–10.48	5.5–9.0	5.5–9.0
Conductivity (mhos/cm)	0.095–0.765	0.012–0.825	0.059–0.920	–	–
TDS (mg/L)	31–382	28–615	35–428	2100	–
Sodium (ppm)	4–65	1–48	1–7	–	60
Potassium (ppm)	2–89	1–36	2–38	–	–
Calcium (ppm)	3–42	1–48	1–48	–	–
Magnesium (ppm)	1–40	1–36	2–43	–	–
Manganese (ppm)	<0.0015–0.035	<0.0015–0.039	<0.0015–0.038	–	–
Copper (ppm)	<0.001–0.038	<0.001–0.035	<0.001–0.045	3	–
Iron (ppm)	<0.05–2.36	<0.05–0.752	<0.05–0.683	–	–
Zinc (ppm)	<0.0005–0.352	<0.0005–0.225	<0.0005–0.728	5	–
Lead (ppm)	<0.01–0.415	<0.01–0.386	<0.01–0.421	0.1	–

Table 2. Summary of the leachate analysis of CSEB-E CCR samples

Parameters	FA	BA	PA	(IS : 2490, 1981)	
				Inland surface water	Onland for irrigation
pH	5.99-10.12	5.62-9.5	6.74-10.06	5.5-9.0	5.5-9.0
Conductivity (mhos/cm)	0.396-1.128	0.065-0.858	0.092-0.945	-	-
TDS (mg/L)	49-439	25-412	30-453	2100	-
Sodium (ppm)	1-89	1-86	2-43	-	-
Potassium (ppm)	1-56	1-36	3-36	0.1	-
Calcium (ppm)	1-57	1-40	1-57	-	-
Magnesium (ppm)	1-96	1-35	1-59	-	-
Manganese (ppm)	<0.0015-0.187	<0.0015-0.054	<0.0015-0.214	3	-
Copper (ppm)	<0.001-0.038	<0.001-0.035	<0.001-0.164	5	-
Iron (ppm)	<0.05-1.408	<0.05-1.218	<0.05-1.463	-	-
Zinc (ppm)	<0.0005-0.661	<0.0005-0.549	<0.0005-0.046	-	60
Lead (ppm)	<0.01-1.541	<0.01-0.419	<0.01-0.125	-	-

Table 3. Summary of the leachate analysis of CSEB-W CCR samples

Parameters	FA	BA	PA	(IS : 2490, 1981)	
				Onland for water	Inland surface irrigation
pH	5.85-9.03	6.34-9.12	6.2-8.73	5.5-9.0	5.5-9.0
Conductivity (mhos/cm)	0.062-0.848	0.125-0.891	0.101-0.789	-	-
TDS (mg/L)	14-432	25-432	20-439	2100	-
Sodium (ppm)	2-64	1-75	1-63	-	60
Potassium (ppm)	1-56	2-98	1-68	-	-
Calcium (ppm)	1-42	1-48	1-75	-	-
Magnesium (ppm)	1-42	1-42	1-71	-	-
Manganese (ppm)	<0.0015-0.108	<0.0015-0.043	<0.0015-0.149	-	-
Copper (ppm)	<0.001-0.048	<0.001-0.127	<0.001-0.035	3	-
Iron (ppm)	<0.05-1.852	<0.05-1.568	<0.05-1.198	-	-
Zinc (ppm)	<0.0005-0.48	<0.0005-0.310	<0.0005-0.425	5	-
Lead (ppm)	<0.01-0.692	<0.01-0.26	<0.01-0.298	0.1	-

Table 4. Summary of the leachate analysis of BCPP CCR samples

Parameters	FA	BA	PA	(IS : 2490, 1981)	
				Onland for water	Inland surface irrigation
pH	6.04-9.92	5.54-9.5	6.79-10.67	5.5-9.0	5.5-9.0
Conductivity (mhos/cm)	0.411-1.175	0.081-0.845	0.191-0.955	-	-
TDS (mg/L)	55-485	35-400	33-525	2100	-
Sodium (ppm)	2-51	1-45	1-48	-	60
Potassium (ppm)	2-47	1-40	1-51	-	-
Calcium (ppm)	1-79	1-45	1-67	-	-
Magnesium (ppm)	1-98	1-61	1-38	-	-
Manganese (ppm)	<0.0015-0.092	<0.0015-0.064	<0.0015-0.210	-	-
Copper (ppm)	<0.001-0.240	<0.001-0.290	<0.001-0.046	3	-
Iron (ppm)	<0.05-3.120	<0.05-3.147	<0.05-4.523	-	-
Zinc (ppm)	<0.0005-0.965	<0.0005-0.586	<0.0005-0.492	5	-
Lead (ppm)	<0.01-0.48	<0.01-0.32	<0.01-0.064	0.1	-

Table 5. Summary of the leachate analysis of CCR samples

Parameters	OPCE	ASTM column	ASTM 24 h shake test	Acid digest test	TCLP
pH	5.54–10.67	5.25–7.68	5.38–8.65	–	4.25–5.48
Conductivity (mhos/cm)	0.012–1.025	0.052–0.452	0.025–0.328	–	2.225–5.65
TDS (mg/L)	14–615	31–225	18–56	–	1.68–78
Sodium (ppm)	1–89	9–42	9.5–38	10.5–40	25–34
Potassium (ppm)	1–98	7–45	7–20	5–31	2.9–22
Calcium (ppm)	1–79	3–68	1.63–21	0.48–14	4–12.25
Magnesium (ppm)	1–98	2–42	1.28–15	1.205–13	1.25–17
Manganese (ppm)	<0.0015–0.214	<0.0015–0.104	<0.0015–0.052	<0.0015–0.085	<0.0015–0.225
Copper (ppm)	<0.001–0.290	<0.001–0.019	<0.001–0.056	<0.001–0.058	<0.001–0.176
Iron (ppm)	<0.05–4.523	<0.05–4.79	<0.036–4.56	<2.23–15.20	<0.015–4.82
Zinc (ppm)	<0.0005–0.965	<0.0005–0.31	<0.0005–0.768	<0.0005–0.058	<0.0005–0.156
Lead (ppm)	<0.01–1.541	<0.01–0.124	<0.01–0.042	<0.01–0.086	<0.01–0.242
Chromium (ppm)	<0.003	<0.003	<0.003–0.035	<0.003–0.0456	<0.003
Nickel (ppm)	<0.009	<0.009	<0.009	<0.009–0.062	<0.009
Cobalt (ppm)	<0.004	<0.004	<0.004	<0.004–0.0287	<0.004

Different leaching techniques showed marked differences in leachate water chemistry, depending on reaction time and water/solid or with column length and flow rate²⁴. Acid digest test, 24 h shake test and TCLP were performed under acidic conditions which led to rapid dissolution of the elements compared to the ASTM column and Open percolation column experiments.

During the process of formation of CCRs at high temperatures, many reactions take place simultaneously. The elements are embedded in the matrix of aluminosilicate oxide³². This may lead to controlled release of elements during leaching. Two opposing processes are known to establish the pH of the leachate. Thus, the dissolution and hydrolysis of oxide components such as CaO and MgO contribute to increase in pH. Ricou, Hequet have reported pH to influence as follows :

- pH > 6 Precipitation
- 6 < pH < 5 Adsorption and surface phenomenon
- pH < 5 Competitive adsorption

The different leaching behavior of elements is a function of elemental properties, pH of the solution and leaching time^{33,24,34,25}. The trace-element leaching was found to be slower which may be due to time required for dissolution of bulk matrix³⁵. It is suggested that the leaching of trace elements is affected by the number of extractions.

The electrical conductivity values decreased progressively and the highest values were observed in the first extraction. Therefore, cation concentrations decreased after each extraction. Thus the mobility of these trace elements is directly affected by the pH of the leaching solution^{36,37}.

Results and discussion

The pH values of all the samples as observed from Open Percolation Column Studies were found to be alkaline in nature in the long run. The pH of the fly ash samples were more acidic in nature compared to bottom ash and pond ash samples. This may be due to high surface area of fine sized particles and greater adsorption of elements on them. This is also supported by the rapid dissolution of elements and initial high values of heavy metals in leachates.

The pH of the leachate was initially controlled by the alkalinity of the CCR sample. The maximum pH in all leachants was between 5.54 (BCPP-BA) and 10.67 (BCPP-PA) (Table 4). The existence of Ca, Mg, Na and K in the acidic and alkaline leachate throughout the study period may be attributed to their solubility in a broad range of pH values. Most metallic cations appear to be more soluble in acid solutions as the high concentration of Fe, Cu, Co and Ni was found during acid digest test.

The initial high concentrations of the elements in the CCR samples were mainly of those associated with the surface which showed a rapid release. However, the elements incorporated within the interior of the CCR matrix dissolved in a slower mode compared with the readily leachable surface-associated elements.

pH was found to be within the permissible limits as per Indian standards (IS : 2490) except slight fluctuations. Mostly the pH remained in neutral to slightly alkaline range. This alkaline nature of the CCRs can be used in amending acidic soils and derelict mined lands.

Conductivity also showed a similar trend with initial high value and then decreased gradually with time. The minimum (0.012 mmhos/cm) and maximum (1.025 mmhos/cm) (Table 5) values were observed for KSTPS-BA and CSEB-E FA respectively. Conductivity is directly related to total dissolved solids which varied from 14 (CSEB-W FA) to 615 ppm (KSTPS-BA) (Table 5). It represents the availability of surficial elements like sodium, potassium, calcium and magnesium. It decreases with the increase in number of leachings, recording highest values of leaching in the first leachates. This is further confirmed from the leachate analysis where sudden decrease of conductivity gives rise to a decrease in concentration levels of the surficial elements.

Sodium, potassium, calcium and magnesium were found to leach throughout the study period and they varied from 1 to 89 ppm (CSEB-E FA), 1–98 ppm (CSEB-W BA), 1–79 ppm (BCPP-FA) and 1–98 ppm (BCPP-FA) (Table 5) respectively. The reason might be attributed to their surficial presence and continuous release into the leachate solution. This also contributes towards the alkaline nature of the leachates which is also supported by the neutral pH ranges observed during wash out of these surficial elements. Sodium and calcium are known to be associated with the surface of CCRs as the main components of aluminosilicate glass fractions^{38,2}.

This can be observed from the open column leachate results where initial concentration levels were generally observed two to four times greater than those residues that had been leached for as little as two to three months later. The loosely held surficial elements were hardly available again for leaching after the first flush phenomenon. The concentration of surficial elements with time

clearly shows the decreasing trend with time. Decrease in conductivity values with time also supports the washing out of surficial elements to a greater extent. Higher levels of some of the leachable elements were observed in the open column results.

Leachates of open column percolation experiments from all the CCR samples were analyzed for twenty-three elements. The concentration of chromium, nickel, cobalt, cadmium, selenium, aluminum, silver, arsenic, boron, barium, vanadium, antimony, molybdenum and mercury in the leachates was below detection limit during the entire study period. The remaining nine elements like iron, lead, magnesium, calcium, copper, zinc, manganese, sodium and potassium were observed in the leachates. Iron, copper, lead, zinc and manganese did not show a regular leaching trend and showed intermittent behavior and finally reduced to negligible limits. They were generally close to the detection limits (Table 5).

The leaching behavior of CCRs indicates that the surface associated elements dominate the leachate chemistry during the early stages of ash disposal in water. However, as the leaching progresses, further weathering releases the elements incorporated within the matrix which gradually decreases with time.

In all the nine leached elements initial high concentration was observed with time and finally either the concentration reduced considerably or reduced to negligible value. The discharge of leachates with these characteristics is not likely to cause any contamination problem^{39,40}. In open column percolation experiments, the rate of water percolation was controlled directly by gravity and permeability of the sample packed in the columns having high solid to liquid ratio of 200 : 1. For an element that was easily leachable or is a major component of the CCRs, the impact of solid to liquid ratio was small. Elements that were present in higher concentrations in CCRs gradually declined in concentration with time.

Conclusions :

Calcium, magnesium, sodium and potassium were observed at higher concentration levels compared to other elements of leachates from open column percolation experiments. The concentration of various elements in the ash pond effluents was found to be slightly higher than the laboratory conditions which may be understood keep-

ing in view that actual ash pond receives fresh ash at regular intervals and leaching of which is responsible for these elevated values.

It can be inferred that no significant leaching occurs and toxicity was manageable with respect to trace elements in the open column percolation experiments. The physical set up of the open columns more closely resembles the field situations, as leaching takes place under the action of gravity and the solid to liquid ratio is more close to the field situation. Overall, leachates of open column percolation experiment and ash pond effluents do not pose any environmental threat as far as leaching of trace elements/toxic metals are concerned. In fact, the open percolation experiments best simulate the field conditions and are the most reliable in predicting the long term leaching behavior.

Notations :

FA, Fly Ash; BA, Bottom Ash; PA, Pond Ash; KSTPS, Korba Super Thermal Power Station; CSEB-E, Chhattisgarh State Electricity Board-East; CSEB-W, Chhattisgarh State Electricity Board-West; BCPP, Balco Captive Power Plant.

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